

Tooth-Supported Maxillary Overdentures: Revisiting Concepts and Applications.

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Abstract

Tooth-supported maxillary overdentures offer a practical and biologically favourable solution for partially edentulous patients, preserving alveolar bone and enhancing proprioception. This case report highlights the rehabilitation of a maxillary arch using retained natural teeth as abutments, emphasizing improved prosthesis stability, patient comfort, and masticatory efficiency. Endodontic treatment and copings were utilized to support the overdenture. The approach is cost-effective and particularly beneficial for patients unsuitable for implants. Successful outcomes depend on appropriate case selection, meticulous planning, and regular follow-up. This technique integrates preventive prosthodontic principles for optimal functional and aesthetic restoration.

Keywords- Overdenture, Residual ridge resorption, Retention, Support.

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Introduction

Edentulism is a significant dental health concern, often leading to functional, aesthetic and psychological challenges for patients. The absence of teeth contributes to a host of problems, including reduced masticatory efficiency, impaired speech, compromised facial aesthetics and diminished self-confidence. One of the most critical consequences of edentulism is the rapid resorption of the alveolar ridge, which not only complicates prosthetic rehabilitation but also accelerates facial aging and functional impairment.^[1,2]

Conventional complete dentures have long been a standard treatment modality for edentulous patients. However, these prostheses are often associated with reduced retention and stability, particularly in cases of

severe ridge resorption. Additionally, the absence of natural teeth or roots further exacerbates the rate of residual ridge resorption, compromising the long-term functionality and comfort of these prostheses.^[3]

To address these limitations, tooth-supported overdentures have emerged as a viable and practical solution within the realm of preventive prosthodontics. A tooth-supported overdenture is a removable prosthesis that utilizes retained natural teeth or their roots as support. This approach not only improves retention and stability but also offers significant advantages in terms of alveolar bone preservation, periodontal health and proprioception.^[4,5] By preserving the natural tooth roots, the periodontal ligament remains intact, enhancing tactile sensitivity and

reducing ridge resorption. These benefits lead to improved masticatory efficiency and better patient acceptance of the prosthesis.^[6,7]

Furthermore, tooth-supported overdentures present a cost-effective alternative to implant-supported overdentures, particularly for patients with financial constraints or anatomical limitations such as inadequate bone volume for implant placement. The biological and psychological advantages of retaining natural teeth make this treatment modality a preferred choice for many patients.^[8]

The success of a tooth-supported overdenture depends on meticulous case selection and treatment planning. Adequate interocclusal space must be ensured for the inclusion of attachments, copings or modifications of retained teeth. Additionally, the preservation of the remaining teeth requires careful periodontal and endodontic management, ensuring the longevity of the prosthesis.^[9,10]

This case report discusses the rehabilitation of a maxillary arch using a tooth-supported overdenture, emphasizing the advantages of this approach in enhancing prosthesis stability, preserving alveolar bone and improving overall patient satisfaction. The report highlights the importance of integrating preventive prosthodontic principles to optimize functional and aesthetic outcomes.

Case Report

A female patient, of 63-years of age, visited the Prosthodontics and Crown & Bridge department at I.T.S Dental College, Muradnagar, Ghaziabad. The patient complained of inability to eat and wanted a better aesthetic appearance. On evaluating the patient clinically, the diagnosis of the patient

was partially edentulous with respect to maxillary and mandibular arches. Teeth present in the maxilla were 13,18,23 and 27 (Figure 1). Favourable bone height and width, with adequate bone support was present with respect to the maxillary arch on radiographic evaluation.

The patient was informed about different treatment options:

1. Full mouth extraction of teeth followed by complete denture in maxillary arch and removable partial denture in mandibular arch.
2. Implant supported overdenture in maxillary arch and removable partial denture in mandibular arch.
3. Root canal therapy of the existing teeth followed by tooth supported overdenture in maxillary arch and removable partial denture in mandibular arch.

After a thorough explanation of the treatment plan and obtaining informed consent from the patient, it was decided to utilize the remaining teeth as abutments and fabricate a tooth-supported overdenture for the maxillary arch and a removable partial denture for the mandibular arch. Upon evaluation, the grade III mobile teeth in the lower arch were deemed non-restorable and indicated for extraction. Following their extraction, impressions of the lower arch were made. Oral prophylaxis and pocket removal was done for existing teeth. Endodontic therapy was performed on teeth 13, 18, 23, and 27. To create adequate space for the overlying denture, the crown portions were prepared (Figure 2). 2 to 3 mm of tooth structure, present above the alveolar ridge. Additional silicone was used for making impression for the fabrication of coping (Figure 3). The fit of the copings was checked in the patient's mouth and glass ionomer cement was used for cementation (Figure 4 and 5).

Irreversible hydrocolloid was used for primary impressions of maxillary and mandibular arches. Using dental stone, impression was poured and on the diagnostic cast, custom trays were fabricated with double wax sheet spacer and self-cure acrylic resin (Cold Cure Denture Base Material). In the maxillary arch, with the help of low fusing impression compound, border moulding was done. After removing the spacer from the trays, final impression was recorded with the help of medium viscosity rubber base material. Dental stone, was used to pour the impression. On the master cast, undercuts were blocked, followed by the occlusal rims were made and jaw relations were recorded. The establish records were transferred to an articulator and the arrangement of teeth was done. After try in verification in patient mouth, the maxillary complete denture and mandibular partial denture were processed. The denture is processed, trimmed, finished and polished. Retention and any sharpness were evaluated intraorally. Finally, the dentures were delivered and their maintenance guidelines were advised (Figure 6). Patient showed satisfaction with the dentures during insertion appointment. The patient was reviewed a day later, after, 1 week and after one month.

Discussion

Tooth-supported overdentures have become a popular treatment option for patients with a few remaining natural teeth, offering several advantages over traditional complete dentures and even implant-supported prostheses. The primary benefit of a tooth-supported overdenture lies in its ability to preserve the remaining alveolar bone and provide superior proprioception compared to complete dentures. This treatment approach helps reduce the rate of ridge resorption and maintains the integrity of the periodontal ligament, allowing patients to retain more

natural sensory feedback during chewing and other oral functions.

The concept of overdentures is rooted in the idea of supporting a removable prosthesis on natural teeth or roots, which can be especially beneficial for the maxillary arch, where the stability of complete dentures can be challenging due to high palatal vaults or unfavorable muscle attachments. The overdenture design involves modifying and preserving the natural teeth, often through root canal therapy and the use of cast copings, to ensure that they provide sufficient support for the prosthesis. In the maxillary arch, two canines are typically selected as abutments due to their strategic location and ability to withstand the occlusal forces. In cases where anterior teeth are compromised, posterior teeth may also be used as abutments.

Rissin et al. demonstrated that overdenture wearers exhibited superior masticatory performance compared to patients with conventional complete dentures, showing increased efficiency and better chewing performance.¹¹ The use of a tooth-supported overdenture, especially in the maxilla, helps maintain proprioception, which is often lost in completely edentulous patients. This preserved sensory feedback contributes to improved bite force awareness, helping patients maintain better neuromuscular control during chewing.

Furthermore, overdentures provide a psychological advantage, offering patients a sense of retaining their natural teeth and thus improving their self-esteem. For many edentulous patients, the psychological benefits of retaining natural teeth in an overdenture far outweigh the considerations of cost and treatment complexity. While implant-supported prostheses may offer even greater stability, they are often not feasible due to anatomical, medical, or financial constraints.¹² Overdentures thus provide a viable alternative,

especially when only a few teeth are remaining.

The main challenge in the fabrication of a maxillary tooth-supported overdenture lies in ensuring adequate retention and stability. Various techniques can be used to modify the remaining natural teeth, ranging from simple tooth reduction to the preparation of more complex cast copings and the use of attachments.¹³ In the case of compromised teeth, endodontic therapy is often required to maintain the health of the abutments. Ball and socket attachments or other types of flexible attachment systems can further enhance the retention of the overdenture, particularly when there is limited vertical space.¹⁴

The success of a maxillary tooth-supported overdenture is dependent on careful treatment planning and proper case selection. The patient's oral hygiene habits must be closely monitored, as the maintenance of natural teeth is crucial to the long-term success of the prosthesis. Periodic follow-up appointments, including radiographs, are necessary to monitor the health of the abutments and the surrounding tissues. The use of short metal copings in overdentures can help distribute occlusal forces more evenly, thereby reducing the risk of abutment fractures and maintaining the stability of the prosthesis.¹⁵

Tooth-supported overdentures also offer an economically viable option for patients who may not be candidates for implant therapy. By retaining natural teeth, patients can avoid the cost and complexity of implants while still achieving functional and aesthetic restoration. The preservation of the remaining alveolar bone, reduction in vertical dimension, and maintenance of proprioception make tooth-supported overdentures a comprehensive solution for the edentulous patient.

Conclusion

Maxillary tooth-supported overdentures represent an important treatment modality for

patients with few remaining teeth. They offer numerous advantages, including the preservation of the alveolar bone, maintenance of proprioception and enhanced masticatory function. While they may not be suitable for all patients, careful case selection and proper treatment planning can make them an excellent alternative to traditional dentures or implant-supported prostheses. The key to success lies in ensuring adequate retention, modifying the remaining teeth effectively and closely monitoring the patient's oral hygiene and follow-up care.

References

1. Atwood DA. Post-extraction changes in the adult mandible as illustrated by microradiographs of midsagittal sections and serial cephalometric roentgenograms. *J Prosthet Dent.* 1963;13(5):810–24.
2. Tallgren A. The continuing reduction of the residual alveolar ridges in complete denture wearers: a mixed-longitudinal study covering 25 years. *J Prosthet Dent.* 1972;27(2):120–32.
3. Winkler S. *Essentials of complete denture prosthodontics*. 2nd ed. St. Louis: Ishiyaku EuroAmerica; 2000.
4. Morrow RM, Rudd KD, Rhoads JE. *Dental laboratory procedures: complete dentures*. 3rd ed. St. Louis: Mosby; 1986.
5. Crum RJ, Rooney GE. Alveolar bone loss in overdentures: a 5-year study. *J Prosthet Dent.* 1978;40(6):610–3.
6. Burns DR. The mandibular complete overdenture. *Dent Clin North Am.* 2004;48(3):603–23.
7. Toolson LB, Smith DE. A five-year longitudinal study of patients treated

- with overdentures. *J Prosthet Dent.* 1978;40(5):494–7.
8. MacEntee MI, Walton JN, Glick N. A clinical trial of patient satisfaction and prosthetic performance with mandibular implant overdentures. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Implants.* 2005;20(6):758–66.
9. Wismeijer D, Vermeeren JI, Mulder J. Clinical and radiological results of patients with immediate overdentures supported by two IMZ implants in the lower jaw. *J Oral Rehabil.* 1992;19(6):595–603.
10. DeVan MM. The concept of preservation in prosthodontic rehabilitation. *J Prosthet Dent.* 1952;2(4):398–405.
11. Rissin L, House JE, Manly RS, Kapur KK. Clinical comparison of masticatory performance and electromyographic activity in denture wearers. *J Prosthet Dent.* 1978;39(4):458–63.
12. Zarb GA, Bolender CL, Eckert SE, Fenton AH, Jacob RF, Mericske-Stern R. *Prosthodontic treatment for edentulous patients: complete dentures and implant-supported prostheses.* 12th ed. St. Louis: Mosby; 2004.
13. Sadowsky SJ. Mandibular implant-retained overdentures: a literature review. *J Prosthet Dent.* 2001;86(5):468–73.
14. Burns DR. Mandibular implant overdenture treatment: consensus and controversy. *J Prosthodont.* 2000;9(1):37–46.
15. Schmitt A, Zarb GA. The longitudinal clinical effectiveness of osseointegrated dental implants for single-tooth replacement. *Int J Prosthodont.* 1993;6(2):197–202.

FIGURES

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6